

**“STRATEGIES FOR MU UNIVERSITY TUTORS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS’
CREATIVE PROBLEM-SOLVING. STUDENTS’ OPINION”**

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Abstract

This article may be used by MU instructors to examine the methods they employ to help university students build their capacity for original problem-solving. The efficiency of contemporary lecturers' methods of instruction is examined in this study through the idea of the students. Analysing instructional options chosen by students and available to MU professors to foster their creative problem-solving abilities is the main goal. Additionally, we gathered data by using a questionnaire to examine the perspectives of the pupils and from this indicates that fifty fifth-grade kids from MU took part in the study. Potential reasons for the facts and beliefs gathered from students that conflict with the findings of other researchers are also argued. In general, teachers at MU University should generally present more projects that encourage students to think creatively, analyse specific issues, and plan games and quizzes.

Keywords: Teaching methods, lecturers, MU students, opinions, development, and creative problem-solving.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background information

Even after over 60 years of studies, there are still misconceptions about how to evaluate, use, or enhance creativity, despite the fact that it is a phenomenon that has been researched by a wide range of experts. Creativity can be studied from various perspectives. Encouragement, blind variability, divergent thinking, the capacity to identify novel issues, the process of turning an idea into a product, a special cognitive skill, and the development of fresh and practical concepts via experience have all been considered components of creativity [Walia, 2019].

1.2. Specific information

Students may practice and develop their creative abilities and learn how to solve issues on their own by using self-directed thinking. The ability to be attentive to a situation and recognize it as an issue that needs to be solved is the first step in developing creative thinking skills. Being creative is crucial for every learner. Thinking skills that include fluency, adaptability, creativity, and the capacity to explain concepts established to produce new ideas and improve metacognition are referred to as creative thinking talents. [Zulirfan et al., 2022].

As a result, in order to effectively develop this skill, it is crucial that students actively participate in educational settings. According to the World Economic Forum [2018], one of the most important employment skills for 2020 and beyond is creativity.

1.3. Aim

The purpose of this study is to clarify that how students discover the way the teachers deliver their classes. Therefore, this study investigates instructional practices that enhance students' problem-solving abilities.

1.4. Scope

The information of this research project involved fifty Millat Umidi University students in Uzbekistan.

1.5. Outline

The study provides information through the literature review, methods, results, discussion, and conclusion sections.

2. Literature review

2.1. Overview

Students' problem-solving abilities are influenced by intellectual quality, learning materials, learning strategies, and approaches to problem-solving training. Learning methodologies and problem-solving instruction strategies are the key factors consequently, research studies have been carried out to identify effective teaching methods for developing problem-solving skills (Al Mutairi, 2015; Plass, Homer and Kinzer, 2015; Hidayanti, Rochintaniawati and Agustin, 2018; Kailani, Newton and Pedersen, 2019), as well as unconventional methods (Shah's research, 2020; Tsai, 2023; Siti Wulan Sari, Azhar and Zulirfan Zulirfan, 2023).

2.2. Effective teaching methods

Game-Based learning

According to Plass, Homer and Kinzer [2015] and Kailani, Newton and Pedersen [2019], game-based learning creates the foundation for authentic learning since it can mimic or replicate actual life. Across all ages and academic levels, game-based learning fosters the development of problem-solving skills. It's crucial to remember, though, that games do not always indicate beneficial effects. It is necessary to take into account the various elements that complement game-based learning. These elements include the technical proficiency and dispositions of those using the technology, such as researchers, parents, faculty, and classroom teachers. Furthermore, the development of good pedagogical practices around the use of game-based learning is linked to favourable impact. In addition to having a well-executed implementation plan, the content of that execution must be carefully thought out and relevant to the curriculum. The development of problem-solving abilities was more significantly impacted by games with collaborative features including role-playing, peer evaluation, and social gameplay than by games without these features.

These components must therefore be included when creating a game-based learning environment for students.

Brainstorming

An American advertising executive named Alex Osborn first proposed brainstorming, one of the constructivist techniques, in 1953 as a way to get ideas from a group of people in an effort to solve a problem. When he saw that conventional business meeting formats were not producing

innovative ideas, he devised this tactic. [Hidayanti, Rochintaniawati and Agustin, 2018]

The research from Al Mutairi [2015] also demonstrated that brainstorming can greatly enhance students' capacity for original thought when studying science. This was due to the fact that brainstorming requires students to actively participate in the process of teaching and learning. Their active participation allows them to expand their knowledge both individually and in groups as they work creatively to solve presented problems.

2.3. Extraordinary methods

Learner-Centred Instruction (LCI)

Based on Shah's research [2020] and Tsai's research [2023] and Learner-Centred Instruction (LCI) promotes active learning and empowers students to take responsibility for their education. This teaching method emphasises hands-on inquiry, problem solving, and teamwork as necessary for knowledge building. LCI fosters a culture of curiosity, investigation, and innovation, preparing students to tackle a quickly changing, dynamic world. According to the Cone of Learning paradigm, the most efficient way to learn is through firsthand experiences, followed by practice, listening, and reading.

CPS Model (Creative Problem-Solving Model)

In addition, students' creative thinking abilities are intended to be enhanced via CPS-based components, and this CPS model concentrates on problem-solving techniques that choose and refine student answers to particular issues. Apart from mindless memorisation, problem-solving abilities also improve students' cognitive processes. The four domains of creative thinking—fluency, flexibility, originality, evaluation, and elaboration—are improved. [Siti Wulan Sari, Azhar and Zulirfan, 2023].

CBL (Case-based learning)

According to Sistermans [2020] a teaching approach called case-based learning, or CBL, assists students in honing their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities in the way that will benefit them the most. The use of case studies as an alternative to more traditional modes of didactic training has gained popularity among educational reformers in recent years, especially those in higher education. Professional skill development could greatly benefit from case-based learning [Kantar and Massouh, 2015].

2.4. Research gap

The present studies frequently looks at broad approaches to problem solution, with a

primary focus on the instructional strategies and institutional frameworks of lecturers. Additionally, critical thinking techniques are frequently underestimated, especially science-based approaches or systemic problem-solving models. There is a knowledge gap on how tutors' methods and students' requirements coincide since there is a dearth of research that takes into account students' perspectives on the best ways to encourage creative problem-solving. This study explores the teaching methods that MU instructors can use to help MU students hone their innovative problem-solving abilities.

3. Methods

This chapter covers the research respondents, ethical issues and considerations, subjects for investigation, and methodology employed in the study.

3.1. Research respondents

50 students from MU level 5 groups were included in the research. Interestingly, fifty percent of these were males, while the other fifty percent were females (see Appendix 2). Four of the 50 participants are between the ages of 21 and 24, while 46 are between the ages of 18 and 20 (see Appendix 1).

3.2. Research instruments

A single research technique used in the study was a questionnaire asking students about their perceptions of teaching methods and problem-solving abilities. Two of the fifteen questions on the Google Forms-created survey were intended to gather demographic information. The remaining ones dealt with how students perceived their ability to solve problems and how well lecturers' methods worked. The survey was distributed via Telegram messenger in Level 5 MU group chats and across channels. Due of its adaptability, the use of student surveys was recommended.

3.3. Ethical concerns

Participants, namely MU students, were told about the objective of our research, as well as its advantages, study scope, and anonymity, at the beginning of the questionnaire, in the description section. To avoid misunderstandings, no questions about sensitive or personal matters were asked in either the questionnaire (see Appendix 16).

4. Results

Best teaching practices and student recommendations for lecturers will be covered in the report's section on survey results.

4.1. Questionnaire results / Students Perception

In order to determine both the most and least successful teaching methods, MU students were invited to complete a questionnaire. The following bar charts illustrate the most and least

successful methods for fostering students' capacity for original problem-solving. Students believe that the most effective approach is problem-solving quizzes and games, whereas the least effective is active listening (see the Appendices 9 and 10).

Table 1. Most Effective Teaching Methods

Table 2. Least Effective Teaching Methods

In response to the next question concerning the best ways for module lecturers to increase students' creative problem-solving skills, 62% believe that project-based learning, or tackling real-world problems, is the best strategy for the 'Research Project' module (see Appendix 11). The option "Identifying students' potential for problem solving in specific industries" had the most options, accounting for 76% for the 'Microeconomics' module (see Appendix 12), 74% for 'Marketing Insights and Analytics', 'Organisational Behaviour', and 'Managing and running a small business' (see Appendices 13, 14 and 15).

5. Discussion

5.1. Introduction

The primary focus of this study was on effective teaching tactics that would help participants increase their creative problem-solving abilities. The most significant findings will be examined and analysed in this section.

5.2. Major finding

According to a major investigation, problem-solving quizzes and games are the most successful teaching methods, whereas active listening is the least successful. The reason for this is unknown, but it is possible that simply listening is a monotonous method for students because it fails to involve them in the problem-solving process, whereas quizzes and games are popular because students can learn from one another and develop novel approaches to difficult problems with fun.

Plass, Homer, and Kinzer [2015] and Kailani, Newton, and Pedersen [2019] have all found comparable results. According to their research, game-based learning approaches are more advantageous and successful than conventional ones.

5.3. Expected outcome

Furthermore, while students were asked about improvement of the 'Research Project' module. They recommended taking on projects since they usually entail coming up with answers to challenging problems or real-world situations. Students can see the real-world uses of their problem-solving abilities, which gives the process more significance and relevance.

This result is consistent with research showing that project-based learning is a successful teaching strategy by Sistermans [2020] and Kantar and Massouh [2015].

5.4. Interesting finding

The fact that students recommended the integration of the option "Identifying potentials of students to develop problem solving in specific industries" to all other university modules was one of the intriguing discoveries. In their most recent study, Siti Wulan Sari, Azhar, and Zulirfan [2023] offered a similar idea.

6. Limitations

Although there were some noteworthy findings in this paper, the sample size was small—only one-third of the 150 students at Level 5 MU responded—and was not typical of all of the students. It is still possible that other students' viewpoints differ from the respondents. I recommend to improve the external validity of the findings; future studies should strive to use a more representative and varied sample.

Additionally, I had time constraints during my research—more specifically, less than a month to follow submission deadlines to guarantee timely publication. To guarantee excellent, well researched material, it is highly advised that future publishers devote more time and energy to the article development process.

7. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to determine students' perspectives on methods of instruction that improve students' problem-solving skill. After analysing everything, the majority of students demand additional problem-solving quizzes and games to help them strengthen their creative problem-solving skills.

Appendices

Appendix 1

Appendix 2

Appendix 3

3. In your opinion, which of the following is related to problem-solving skills? If other, please specify.

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 4

4. Rate the effectiveness of the "Research Project" subject for developing creative problem-solving skills

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 5

5. Rate the effectiveness of the "Microeconomic s" module for developing creative problem-solving skills

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 6

6. Rate the effectiveness of the "Marketing insights and analytics" subject for developing creative problem-solving skills

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 7

7. Rate the effectiveness of the "Organizational Behaviour" subject for developing creative problem-solving skills

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 8

8. Rate the effectiveness of the "Managing and running a small business" module for developing creative problem-solving skills

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 9

9. Which teaching strategies are MOST effective for developing creative problem-solving (if other, specify)

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 10

10. Which teaching strategies are LEAST effective for developing creative problem-solving (if other, specify)

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 11

11. Please select the best ways for "Research Project" module lecturers to improve students' creative problem-solving skills (if other, specify)

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 12

12. Please select the best ways for "Microeconomic s" module lecturers to improve students' creative problem-solving skills (if other, specify)

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 13

R T

13. Please select the best ways for "Marketing insights and analytics" module lecturers to improve students' creative problem-solving skills (if other, specify)

50 ответов

Appendix 14

14. Please select the best ways for "Organizational Behaviour" module lecturers to improve students' creative problem-solving skills (if other, specify)

50 ответов

Appendix 15

15. Please select the best ways for "Managing and running a small business" module lecturers to improve students' creative problem-solving skills (if other, specify)

Копировать диаграмму

50 ответов

Appendix 16 (Ethical concerns)

Creative methods of teaching problem-solving for MU lectures

B I U

Dear respondent, this study is conducted by Level 5 MU students for their Academic English Coursework. The goal of this questionnaire is to collect data from students in order to find out effective teaching strategies of teaching problem-solving skills for MU lecturers. The collected data will inform teachers about the ways to improve their teaching strategies to develop students' problem solving skills. Your answers are anonymous and will be kept confidential and are gathered only for research purposes. The time for answering questions is up to around 10 minutes.

We are grateful for your responses!

B I U

T

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